

Phytochemical composition of leaf epicuticular waxes of the genus *Chaenomeles* Lindl. introduced plants

Khromykh Nina, Didur Oleh, Anishchenko Andriy
Oles Honchar Dnipro National University (Dnipro, Ukraine)

The plant cuticular waxes component composition is a species-specific feature (Müller & Riederer, 2005). Leaf cuticular waxes (only the inner layer or both the outer and inner, depending on the plant species) participate in limiting extra-stomatal transpiration (Buschhaus et al., 2007; Jetter & Riederer, 2016). Surface epicuticular waxes regulate the wetting, self-cleaning, and light reflection processes, as well as the plant interaction with insects and pathogenic microorganisms (Hansjakob et al., 2011; Łażniewska et al., 2012).

The aim of our study was to establish species-specific properties of leaf cuticular waxes of the genus *Chaenomeles* Lindl. introduced plants as the markers of resistance to the steppe climate. The object of the study conducted in 2020 was the leaves of *Ch. japonica*, *Ch. speciosa*, *Ch. cathayensis*, *Ch. × superba*, and *Ch. × californica* plants in the phase of fully formed leaf blade.

Chloroform extracts of the epicuticular waxes from the upper and lower leaf surfaces were analyzed by GC-MS. The content of individual wax constituents was expressed as a percentage of the identified compounds total amount.

Chromatographic profiles of the epicuticular wax extracts from leaves of species and hybrids of the genus *Chaenomeles* Lindl. had a similar distribution pattern of phytochemical compounds (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Typical chromatogram of leaf epicuticular wax chloroform extracts of the genus *Chaenomeles* introduced plants with the main compounds: 1 – dodecane, 2 – tetradecane, 3 – hexadecane, 4 – octadecane, 5 – heneicosane, 6 – octadecanoic acid, 7 – heptacosane, 8 – di-n-octylphthalate, 9 – tetracontane, 10 – tetratetracontane

The accumulation of epicuticular waxes on the leaf surface varied between the studied species and hybrids of the *Chaenomeles* introduced plants (Table 1).

Table 1

Epicuticular waxes content on the leaf surface of the genus *Chaenomeles* plants
($\bar{x} \pm \text{SD}$, $n = 5$, $P < 0.05$)

Plant species	<i>Ch.</i> <i>japonica</i>	<i>Ch.</i> <i>speciosa</i>	<i>Ch.</i> <i>cathayensis</i>	<i>Ch.</i> × <i>superba</i>	<i>Ch.</i> × <i>californica</i>
Wax content, $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$	64.70 ± 3.88 ^a	80.00 ± 4.23 ^b	85.00 ± 3.95 ^b	78.70 ± 4.11 ^b	70.00 ± 3.69 ^a

Note. Different letters in a row indicate statistically significant differences in the means of the pair being compared (according to the Tukey test).

The results obtained are comparable with data (Jetter & Riederer, 2016) on the accumulation of epicuticular waxes within the range of 25–200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ on the adaxial surface of leaves of plants of different species. The content of epicuticular waxes determined on the leaf surface of peach species and hybrids was higher and varied from 119.5 to 240.1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ (Khromykh et al., 2020).

Currently, the relationship between the accumulation of epicuticular waxes on the leaf surface and plant drought tolerance is not clearly defined, since, along with evidence of positive correlations, many studies have shown that the thickness of the wax layer is not directly related to water loss (Kim et al., 2007; Kosma et al., 2009).

REFERENCES

- Buschhaus, C., Herz, H., & Jetter, R. (2007). Chemical composition of the epicuticular and intracuticular wax layers on adaxial sides of *Rosa canina* leaves. *Annals of Botany*, 100(6), 1557–1564. doi: 10.1093/aob/mcm255
- Hansjakob, A., Riederer, M., & Hildebrandt, U. (2011). Wax matters: absence of very-long-chain aldehydes from the leaf cuticular wax of the glossy11 mutant of maize compromises the prepenetration processes of *Blumeria graminis*. *Plant Pathology*, 60(6), 1151–1161. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-3059.2011.02467.x>
- Jetter, R., & Riederer, M. (2016). Localization of the transpiration barrier in the epi- and intracuticular waxes of eight plant species: water transport resistances are associated with fatty acyl rather than alicyclic components. *Plant Physiology*, 170(2), 921–934. <https://doi.org/10.1104/pp.15.01699>
- Khromykh, N. O., Lykholat, Y. V., Anishchenko, A. A., Didur, O. O., Gaponov, A. A., Kabar, A. M., & Lykholat, T. Y. (2020). Cuticular wax composition of mature leaves of species and hybrids of the genus *Prunus* differing in resistance to clasterosporium disease. *Biosystems Diversity*, 28(4), 370–375. doi: 10.15421/012047
- Kim, K. S., Park, S. H., & Jenks, M. A. (2007). Changes in leaf cuticular waxes of sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.) plants exposed to water deficit. *Journal of Plant Physiology*, 164(9), 1134–1143. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jplph.2006.07.004>
- Kosma, D. K., Bourdenx, B., Bernard, A., Parsons, E. P., Lu, S., Joubes, J., & Jenks, M. A. (2009). The impact of water deficiency on leaf cuticle lipids of *Arabidopsis*. *Plant Physiology*, 151(4), 1918–1929. doi: 10.1104/pp.109.141911
- Łażniewska, J., Macioszek, V., & Kononowicz, A. (2012). Plant-fungus interface: The role of surface structures in plant resistance and susceptibility to pathogenic fungi. *Physiological and Molecular Plant Pathology*, 78, 24–30. doi: 10.1016/j.pmp.2012.01.004
- Müller, C., & Riederer, M. (2005). Plant surface properties in chemical ecology. *Journal of Chemical Ecology*, 31(11), 2621–2651. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10886-005-7617-7>